

FEMALE TRAUMA AND ANXIETY IN RECENT LITERATURE

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Abstract

Greatly literature has influenced the lives of human beings and surely it has given human the power of language to exhibit the inner words of man.

Within the medium of literature women and their writings have been conventionally treated as passive.

This research paper focuses on the trauma and anxiety suffered by the female poets and writers in recent literature .All this anxiety and trauma is projected in the female characters of Alice Walker,Margeret Atwood and Eimear McBride .These protagonists have been abandoned or injured by the society in which they reside .

The portrayal of woman in the writings are considered to be morally and socially tainted ,devalued and stigmatized .

Ultimately the writings of the three writers and poets are more accurate representation of women lives.

Keywords-Trauma,anxiety,tainte,devalued,stigmatized.

INTRODUCTION

Literature has had a profound impact on human life, empowering language to express the depths of our inner world .It provides a space for introspection ,retrospection ,foreshadowing, flashbacks, and poignant memories, often tinged with the pain of past traumas.Now, in the modern world , anxiety takes center stage within literary plots.

Traditionally ,women have been portrayed as passive within the realm of literature. However, contemporary women writers are challenging this demeaning concept. Despite ongoing social and political discussions that continue to stigmatize women it is through women's writing that the role of the'' weaker'' sex in the literary sphere is being established.

This dissertation primarily focuses on the trauma and anxiety experienced by female poets and writers in the recent literature. These women, often neglected or harmed by the society constructed by practical norms, project their anxiety through their female characters. Historically, women who were deemed sexually, morally, or socially tainted were devalued and stigmatized, effectively blacklisted by society.

THEME

Through an exploration into the lives of writers and poets and the female character developed by Alice Walker, Margeret Atwood and Eimear McBride will explore the condition in which the female body and trauma are treated in contemporary fiction and explores their neglect and lack have been portrayed. The three poets and writers focused upon in the paper have been tainted in many ways by the society in which they are depicted suffering due to traumatic life events is a product of the historical and contextual social political expectation and projection inflicted upon their sex with respective writing about the female-specific traumatic experiences. 'In Surfacing' which takes place in Quebec, Canada Atwood first leads the reader along with her friends and family to believe that she has abandoned both her husband and infant child. Through the layers of hidden and rewritten memories created to protect her mental fragility as she searches for her presumed dead father in the wilderness surrounding the old family home it comes to light it is an affair with a married man and a coerced illegal abortion that she has been running from. The importance of Atwood Canadian heritage in connection to her character's feeling of alienation from her own biological autonomy and self are all prevalent in the way the text is written showing the notion of traumatic isolation.

Walker's "The colour purple" set in the early twentieth-century concerns the story of Celie, a poor and uneducated African-American woman living in the post-slavery.

When her mother falls ill Celie is sexually abused by her perfumed father Pa by whom she is twice impregnated. Having to hide her pregnancies for the fear of shame the children have been removed from her care shortly after their birth presuming them to have been drowned suffering the same treatment from her husband to whom she is given by her father she writes a letter to god as a means of coping with the maltreatment she faces.

Eimear McBride's "A girl is half formed thing" protagonist is also sexually abused by her uncle, the husband of her aunt at the age of thirteen. The lasting damage of this event and the ongoing grooming that her uncle engages in being to shape a narrational relationship between sex and violence. As she attempts to come to terms with the inoperable tumor that seals the face of her elder brother and frames her narratives. She is also faced with the lifelong task of attempting to reconcile the distance between herself and her catholic mother.

According to psychologists, trauma theory explains how the mind and body of an individual respond to traumatic experiences. In studies, trauma is often described as being unrepresentable, inexpressible, and difficult to incorporate into a coherent narrative.

The profound impact of trauma can be authentically manifest in literature by artfully mirroring its symptoms, suggesting the disintegration of time and the sequence of events. The fictional characters created by Atwood, Walker and Mc Bride serve as powerful witnesses to the oppression faced by women. Though their own traumatic experiences, these authors shed light

on the political issues women confront. By giving voice to these characters, the novels enhance the reader's understanding and evoke empathy towards these challenges.

OBJECTIVES

- 1 to learn about the trauma and anxiety suffered by the female writers and poets.
- 2 To learn about the writer's protagonists and their hardships
- 3 To learn about the morally and socially tainted portrayal of women in the writings in recent literature.

Data & Methodology

Data is collected from already published texts in the public domain. Literature sources can include textbooks, government and private companies reports, online papers and articles.

Methodology -Literary method is used Impact of trauma and anxiety

The impact of trauma and anxiety can easily be seen in the novels of Alice Walker, Margeret Atwood and Eimear McBride protagonists where they are treated as passive objects, sexually abused by close relatives and friends, devalued, morally and socially tainted and stigmatized.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- 1 The significant role of trauma and psychoanalysis

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Findings

1 It is found in the Atwood's novels where the character makes a critical discovery, she makes a decision to get rid of anything, she rejects to be victimized and to be dominated and controlled by the hunters, she breaks the rules and makes a distance with trauma, her aim is to free herself from the boundaries of the society.

2 The hero gains self knowledge and self confidence to improve her life, she teaches a lesson to the other female characters, she makes a new form of archetypal figure of herself, she becomes an antihero, thus not only there is a woman as a survival but also as a winner.

2 Understanding Identity, Conflict, and Trauma through literary texts on selected women writers of North India

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Findings

1 Writings of the North -East India are products of conflict. once known for its natural comeliness and cultural heritage the north-east part gradually turned out to be other territory famous for ernous reasons

2 Despite passing through a belligerent history of enmity ,distrust,frangibility and blood shed ,a simultaneous effort for peace in north -eastIndia is additionally going on. Peace itself is an inclusive term grounded on the fundamental principles of participation,democracy ,dialogue,transparency ,human rights etc,hence efforts for peace should be fortified

3 For this the Writers appeal to the readers to scrutinize the critical issues then adopt a viable a viable mechanism..

3 Representing Trauma in American women's literature

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Findings

4 Cathy's Caruth's Trauma theory and contemporary Indian fiction

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Findings

1 The proposed study provide the analysis of the selected n f selected texts within the frame work of Cathy Caruth's Trauma theory. With appropriate and concrete illustrations from the selected works , the study attempts to make an in-depth exploration of the concepts and principles advocated by Caruth in her trauma theory like one such prominent writer Arupa Ptangia Kalita in her novel 'The story of Felanee [2011] revolves around a womanm who lives her life surrounded and affected by the fierce conflict between the ethnic -Assamese desiring complete dominance and the Bodos claiming a separate stateb.. The book portrays the traumatised soul of Felanee who has witnessed her village burning and her husband dying amidst of violence

In an article entitled ;Chronicles of pain :The Half Mother through resistance discourse by Jan Mohamad Pandit explores the prolonged silence of mothers whose sons have gone forced disappearance .The paper makes an analysis of the pain ,suffering ,torture and confusion of a kashmiri motherwho only waits and longs to be united with her son.

2 he study not only provides a detailed analysis of the effect of insurgencies on the commonmasses in India but also yield new results to bring forth the literary tradition of the east and the wst ,thus making it a cross cultural study

5 The Impact of Trauma in Literature

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Findings

1 The array of literary, theoretical, historical and cultural texts referred to in this study have provided ample evidence and argument that trauma is frequently caused by human made injustice, oppression, violence and exploitation.

2 Trauma also has meaning in that it is indicative of basic life issues such as the relation between life and death, the meaning and quality of existence whether physical or psychological survival, how people understand and cope with loss and self diminishment.

CONCLUSION

Literature has often depicted women as passive objects within society. This portrayal is evident in the works of Atwood, Walker and McBride, it was discovered that women who are considered to be morally or socially tainted by society are often devalued and stigmatized. In addition to highlighting the psychological impact of traumatic experiences on women's lives, these authors also challenged traditional gender roles through their writings. It is more evident in the essays which outlines the concept of male gaze as a powerful tool for objectifying females in media. By using literary tools such as narrative structure and characterization techniques, these writers were able to effectively portray both physical aspects of female trauma while simultaneously challenging existing social norms about gender identity. Through their protagonists, these writers shed light on the hardships faced by women due to contextual and socio-economic circumstances.

One example of this is evident in the concept of 'In Surfacing' which serves as a metaphor in these literary works. It dramatizes a woman's journey from a fragile sense of self to a state of madness, ultimately leading to the development of a more complete and authentic identity.

By contextualizing the literary works within broader social and historical context we can gain a deeper appreciation for the profound impact of literature in reflecting and addressing the complexities of women's experiences. Ultimately this nuanced exploration will contribute to a more comprehensive analysis of how literature can both perpetuate and challenge gender stereotypes, offering a more accurate representation of women's lives.

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